

Exploring Links: Employee Diversity & Corporate Culture

Promoting Organizational Growth

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Abstract:- The main aim of writing this document is to establish and promote a healthy work culture in various multicultural corporate organizations in present scenario. The study focuses on developing different methods/measures needed to create a better interpersonal relationship among the diverse workforce of different nationalities & genders which are coming together to achieve organizational objectives, thus contributing to the society in one or the other way. As stated in study published in University of Florida, “Managing diversity is more than simply acknowledging differences in people. It involves recognizing the value of differences, combating discrimination, and promoting inclusiveness.” So, I am writing this research paper based on Primary research including the report or statistical data of the current opinions & views of employees from diverse nationalities/culture in different organizations regarding their daily experiences at workplace. I will also include secondary data from different articles, theories on internet to limelight the various measures which can be adopted to overcome the problems faced by the people in day to day work life. The investigation also challenges the opinion that diversity in workforce does not support structured employee training & hampers organizational growth due to several barriers such as Language, work culture etc. So, in a nutshell, this study will concentrate on several measures or implications that should be adopted in general practice by the organizations such as “Employee Handbook”, “Code of Conduct” which will help personnel in achieving their personal growth & will also contribute to professional growth overall exhibiting economic growth to the company.

Keywords: *Managing Diversity, Economic Growth, Code of Conduct, Organizational Growth.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A Diverse workforce is efficient & profitable as it adheres to a pool of innovative & cross-functional experiences contributed by different people belonging to multiple backgrounds, nations, cultures etc. They altogether create a positive mindset on the fact, “**Unity in Diversity**” and also can help any organization achieve tremendous economic growth by performing at their highest level.

According to research cited by Cedric Herring in a 2009 article published in the American Sociological

Review, the most racially diverse companies bring in nearly 15 times more revenue than the least racially diverse. Additionally, Herring found racial diversity to be a better determinant of sales revenue and the amount of customers than company size, age, or the number of employees.

- This shows that employee diversity is an attractive feature which would really help in achieving both organizational & tactical objectives. There a no. of reasons how a diversified workforce can promote a better future to an organization such as:
 - Exchange of Innovative views & ideas.
 - Change in Organizational practices according to several work cultures practiced across the world.
 - Continuous Quality Improvement.
 - Building effective Customer Relationship using diversified branding & advertising.
 - Discovering new talents.
 - Tackle different issues in the organization related to work culture.
 - Growth of the organization globally.
 - Achieving brand equity, ethical sustainability & loyalty in the market.
 - Developing Problem Solving and multi-tasking skills by implementing the thought of employees coming from varied backgrounds through discussions thus enhancing overall organizational sustainability and success.

➤ *Understanding the Workforce Diversity:*

In modern trends due to immense globalization, privatization and networking people have started moving frequently beyond borders which results in organization’s hiring more people from diverse backgrounds irrespective of their culture & beliefs. Recently in a study from Deloitte University Press report on diversity and inclusivity, reveals that nowadays companies have started focusing on workforce diversity as a strategy to more profitability in business.

Also, in developing countries like Africa, many business oriented people are exploring it due to availability of abundant resources and customizing their working according to African culture. Workforce Diversity also includes behavioral, Structural & Social diversity in terms of thinking & learning, creativity, management, age, gender, educational level, marital status, language, etc.

In fact, the recent involvement of women, as an active contributor, in all the top-management positions also speak a lot about the Stereotypical pattern of organizations since long run. According to a , research report conducted by *Nancy M. Carter and Harvey M. Wagner*, companies that have three or more women on the board “outperform companies with all-male boards by 60 percent in return on invested capital, 84 percent in return on sales and 60 percent in return on equity. These numbers suggest that diversity and inclusion are not just profitable; they have a synergistic impact on profits.”

Thus, understanding & managing workforce diversity is a crucial component for the organizations in future to develop core competencies in terms of revenue, brand positioning & maximum profit.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this research paper, author has conducted the study based upon both Primary & Secondary Data.

Primary Research would include statistical data based on the questionnaire which includes the response/feedback of certain employees working in different organizations of Africa. It also emphasize the experiences of people in terms of personal growth & evolving as a human being after being a part of various Multi-National Companies and their cross-functional working style across cultural boundaries.

On the basis of above study, findings will be incorporated in a table format along with the questions used to portray the different opinions of people who were surveyed throughout the research.

- *The Research will Include the Study of Following Points-*
- How diverse is the executive team in your Organization?
 - Do you think your Organization’s promotion and evaluation process is diverse?
 - On a Scale of 1 to 5, how safe do you feel communicating your concerns in the organization?
 - Do you see career growth in your Organization?
 - How well does the HR department invest/manage in hiring candidates from diverse backgrounds?
 - Do you think the training & induction program given to you by your organizations cover all the measures of diversification?
 - On a scale of 1 to 5 how far do you see women employee’s career opportunities in your organization?
 - Does Language become a barrier sometimes while communicating to the local staff in your organization?
 - Does the work culture in your organization affect you personally?
 - On a scale of 1 to 5, to what extent can workforce diversity result in conflict?

The Secondary data would include data research from different websites, study published in journals, articles, theories etc. present on internet regarding Workforce Diversity in various corporate organizations.

The investigation done by the author also includes a representation of various points/parameters important for the survey calculated in percentage in table format using Quantitative Research. The interpretation will be analyzed in detail after the correct findings through the observations done in report or survey.

➤ *Advantages of Workforce Diversity:*

According to research cited by published in the “*American Sociological Review*”, the most racially diverse companies bring in nearly 15 times more revenue than the least racially diverse companies. This study clearly shows that the workforce that belong to different races can actually support the organization in gaining a deeper & broader understanding of profit maximization & developing brand equity globally.

Also, people coming from diverse backgrounds can actually inculcate innovative skills pertaining to their own places which would create a revolution in achieving missions or long term targets in the organization. For instance, migration of people from developing countries of Asian continent to developed countries such as America has proven that the world is ready to welcome new talent & acquisitions across the globe in lieu of gaining modernization & development.

Another vital factor can be developing Problem solving skills which is the major key to success nowadays in most of the production & manufacturing oriented organizations. In recent times, due to various pandemic issues held recently many people suffered a lot of disaster which has affected them personally & professionally.

Organizations need a major setback to handle these kinds of issues in near future which will only be possible if they really persuade divergent ideas & opinion practiced by people from various cultures & backgrounds.

As distinct people have distinct perceptions so they would really help in coming to a solution from separate perspectives if they are involved in some open ended discussions in organizational meetings.

It is also stated that any organization’s main asset is its employees so diversification would also help in evolving Multi-tasking which is another emerging skill required these days to carry out various tasks & jobs by exchanging of ideas, opinions, developing contingency approach etc.

According to *Hubbard*, diversity impacts an individual largely while working in customer markets & gaining market review of customer’s preferences, choices etc. which also helps organizations in adopting new policies & procedures in attaining customer loyalty. Therefore, diversity proves to be less argumentative as it really provides better knowledge & exposure which is required by the organization for well conduction of the business. It also creates a powerful platform for the employees so that they can perform at their highest level.

➤ *Challenges of Employee Diversity:*

There is a famous saying, “**Too many cooks spoil the broth**” which greatly affects the concept of diversity in the management as well. Sometimes individual’s differences create prejudices which hamper the growth of organization. Even the entity obligations to business are affected due to various law practices that are not similar at all places & really becomes a major issue in employee understanding about enforcement of legal procedures in any corporate organization.

There are also cases of harassment and discrimination:

Occasionally in the organization pertaining due to the conflict of opinion between two employees of diverse background or work culture regarding a particular issue that also results in the consequences of decline in organization’s success. Apart from it, language act as a barrier in effective communication between the personnel which also delays some targets & projects that has to accomplished time bound thus resulting in lack of cooperation & efficient team building.

Even the attire or dress code at the workplace can be a crucial challenge in managing & implementing diversity as some of the employees especially women can refuse to follow a particular dress code assign by the management as they would not feel comfortable in that according to their own culture & belief.

According to *Lawrence Herzog of HCareers*, managers face challenges when new employees from diverse backgrounds interact with long-standing employees. Many companies offer training programs to managers to help them effectively manage their newly diverse departments.

Thus to resolve these concerns, management should think upon some policies & strategies to overcome the disturbance which should help in managing workforce diversity.

➤ *Findings & Observations*

Based on the survey through Questionnaire following are the findings & observations through data:-

- No. of Observations (Employees) – 20
- No. of Organizations surveyed – 2-3
- Time taken – 24 hours

➤ *Impact of Diversity on Organizational Performance*

Following is the statistical data through Pie-Chart representation clearly stating the percentage of various factors that are caused by diversification in different organizations:-

Fig 1 Diversification in Organization

Fig 2 Communication

Fig 3 Carrer Growth

Table 1 Effects of Diversification

Factors	Maximum	Minimum	Balanced
Diversification in Organization	20%	70%	10%
Promotion & Evaluation of employees in Organization	80%	20%	-
Communication of Job related concerns	20%	10%	70%
Career Growth	90%	5%	5%
Managing/Hiring Candidates by HR Department	5%	20%	75%
Training & Induction Program	10%	30%	60%
Women’s Career opportunities	20%	30%	50%
Language as a barrier	40%	60%	-
Conflict	20%	70%	10%
Work Culture affecting employees	30%	70%	-

Fig 4 Training & Induction program

Fig 5 Managing / Hiring Candidates by HR

Fig 6 Women’s Career Opportunities

III. ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

- The above study shows a clear picture of the factors that affects the employees working in organizations with a diversified workforce. Some of the major points of concern which the management needs to incorporate in their structure are:
 - Hiring competent & diversified workforce to meet work related problems & achieve a group of multicultural people.
 - More Training & induction programs should be devised according to needs & expectations of employees by consulting some specialized agencies to make them more skilled & comfortable to meet the demands of the management.
 - There should be more career opportunities for women especially on managerial positions to break the monotony and also developing them financially, thus promoting growth & equality of all sections of society.
 - Language proficiency should be improved by providing classes or crash courses to the employees of different nationalities to support their linguistic skills which would thus affect the productivity & expansion of business in particular organization.
 - Organizations like MNC’s who are operating worldwide at different places should involve maximum diversification while hiring candidates in order to have more employee interaction & learning of new and innovative skills.

IV. DISCUSSION

In a research done on computers & mobile phones, it was found that diversification strategy saved many big organizations such as Apple from failure and helped them to grow as a very big organization.

- So, notably, based on the primary research & findings it is quite evident that organizations implementing workforce diversity has a lot of challenges but as all the problems can be handled with appropriate solutions, organizations can adopt certain methods and procedures to overcome these problems such as:

- **Performance appraisal & personnel evaluation** should be done on a separate policy designed by management irrespective of their cultural, social or economic differences.
- All the rules, policies & procedures should be acknowledged, well defined & put together in a form of a document particularly should be termed as “**Employee or Staff handbook**” given at the time of Staff Induction program.
- To ensure more collaboration & cooperation, the organization should put all the rules & regulations under the “**Code of Conduct**” to ensure less of discrimination & inculcate equality in terms of dressing, behavior etc, for everyone at the work place.
- Time to time “**Employee Feedback**” program should be initiated & regulated by the HR department through different kinds of surveys or questionnaires to work upon the loopholes & major key areas related to improve the diversification in the company & also should work towards the shortcomings mentioned in the feedback.
- Special departments such as “**Workforce counseling**” should be created with skilled professionals to tackle the problems or obstacles faced by personnel of different nationalities regarding any particular issue to stop biasness & nepotism and strict measures should be taken against it to create a healthy environment.
- **Women** should be offered equal participation in terms of job opportunities or **Right to work** at all the positions in the company irrespective of education or status according to their qualification and experience to as they are strong pillars and also serve as an important section of society.
- The managers or supervisors should be educated about the importance of diversified workforce and the wonderful & optimistic changes they can imply in the organization which would prove a real asset in the long run by developing better interpersonal relationship contributing to a healthy work culture.

V. CONCLUSION

So, According to the research though there are some challenges while implementing Diversification, still there are various points that can be implemented to manage it & workforce diversity can be executed very effectively & efficiently.

The findings of the research also imply that now the time has come to think about change & adopt new perspectives towards modern culture. Important measures should be taken towards the era of multitasking which focus on people coming together from all over the world & working towards one initiative globally.

The study also aims & reveals various actions that should be taken against work discrimination, unnecessary conflicts, and biasness in terms of gender, education, income, nationality etc. and initiate healthy work culture, conducive environment, safe interaction between employees which would create a real essence of unity in diversity by sharing the similarities & celebrating the differences.

➤ *Conflict of Interests*

The author has not declared any potential conflict of interest.

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➤ “**Strength lies in Differences not in Similarities...**” -
Stephen Covey

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